

Evaluating the applicability of R3-reactivity test (ASTM C1897) to blended systems

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Abstract

R3 test (ASTM C1897) is a successful technique for measuring the reactivity of SCMs. Most benchmarking R3 tests correlate the 7d cumulative heat of a single SCM with the corresponding 28d compressive strength of blended mortar (usually with 30% OPC replacement). However, in ternary blends, SCMs with different reactivities are used in combination. To better correlate their reactivity to compressive strength, this study evaluates the applicability of R3-test directly on the blends. 18 ternary blends were studied with 50% OPC replacement using calcined clays (of varying kaolinite content) and fillers (limestone and recycled concrete fines). The results showed that it is possible to predict the 7d and 28d compressive strengths of blended mortars directly from the 7d-heat of the corresponding blend. This study paves the path for unleashing the potential of R3 test to screen a variety of blends based on their intrinsic reactivity.

Figure

